

CuSO₄·5H₂O : A novel and efficient catalyst for the synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes

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Abstract : bis-Indolylmethanes are synthesized in a one pot coupling of carbonyl compounds and indoles using catalytic amount of CuSO₄·5H₂O at ambient temperature. It is first ever use of CuSO₄·5H₂O in this reaction yielding products in excellent yields without the formation of any side products.

Keywords : bis-Indolylmethanes, CuSO₄·5H₂O, indole, carbonyl compounds.

Introduction

Functionalized indoles or more precisely bis-indolylmethanes have received considerable attention as these are bioactive metabolite of terrestrial and marine origin¹. Vibrindole A is the first characterized indole derivative to exhibit antibacterial activity² against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. albus* and *B. subtilis*. Electrophilic substitution reaction of indole with carbonyl compounds provides convenient route to synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes. Consequently, various catalyst have been reported for the synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes which includes protic acid³ as well as Lewis acids like In(OTf)₃⁴, ion exchange resin⁵, montmorillonite K-10 clay⁶, amberlyst⁷, lithium perchlorate⁸ etc. Even though various procedures are reported, disadvantages including low yield, prolonged reaction times, use of an excess of reagent/catalyst necessitate the development of an alternative route for the synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes.

CuSO₄·5H₂O is cheaper, commercially available and therefore its use in organic synthesis is being carried out extensively. It has already been used in well known name reactions of organic chemistry like Biginelli reaction⁹,

Micheal reaction¹⁰ and also used for the synthesis of quinoxaline derivatives¹¹. This mild Lewis acid has been utilized for selective protection of aldehydes¹² and for tetrahydropyranylation/depyranylation of alcohol and phenol¹³. Because of these utilities and on going trend we were tempted to use this cheap catalysts in the preparation of bis-indolylmethanes. The synthesis of these molecules is of current interest because of their medicinal importance.

Results and discussion

These promising applications and other attractive features of this mild Lewis acid and also in continuation to our own interest in the applications of this mild Lewis acid^{9,10} and in development of indole chemistry¹⁴ we were prompted to use CuSO₄·5H₂O in the synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes. Herein, we report the use of CuSO₄·5H₂O as an inexpensive, nontoxic and readily available mild Lewis acid catalysts for the condensation of indole with carbonyl compounds in methanol leading to the one pot efficient synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes at room temperature (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Table 1. CuSO₄.5H₂O mediated synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Products ^a	Time (h)	Yields ^b (%)	M.p. (°C)
1	Ph	H	3a	2.0	92	124–125 (125–126) ^{4b}
2	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	3b	2.5	93	106–107 (105–106) ^{4c}
3	4-MeO-C ₆ H ₄	H	3c	3.0	89	187–188 (186–187) ^{4b}
4	2-Furyl	H	3d	3.5	85	321–323 (325–327) ^{4d}
5	4-HO-C ₆ H ₄	H	3e	2.5	94	120–121 (121–122) ^{4d}
6	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	3f	2.0	88	223–225 (225–226) ^{4d}
7	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄	H	3g	3.0	92	176–178 (175–176) ^{4b}
8	Me	H	3h	6.0	82	157–158 (157–159) ^{4e}
9	Me	Me	3i	6.0	84	64–66 (65–66) ^{4f}

^aThe products were characterized by comparison of their melting points and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data with those of authentic samples.

^bIsolated yields after recrystallization. ^cValues in parenthesis are lit. m.p.

To begin with methanol (2 ml), benzaldehyde (1.2 mmol), indole (2 mmol) and 5 mol% of CuSO₄.5H₂O were stirred at room temperature for 2 h to afford 3,3'-bis-indolylphenylmethane 3a in 90% yield (Table 1, entry 1). Similarly other aldehydes were reacted with indole in presence of catalytic amount of CuSO₄.5H₂O to afford product in 82–94% yields (Table 1) without the formation any side product viz. dihydroindolo[2,3-*b*]carbazole 4. These results are in contrast to a previous report¹⁵ in which product 4 is obtained by addition of second molecule of aldehyde at C2 of indole resulting into cyclized product.

The reaction completes within 2–6 h and 5 mol% of catalyst is enough to facilitate the reaction to completion.

The use of large amount of catalyst did not improve the yields or reduce the reaction time. However, this reaction did not yield desirable product in the absence of catalyst even after 20 h of reaction time.

In conclusion, the present protocol employing CuSO₄.5H₂O is mild, efficient and environment benign catalyst for the synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes. Products are obtained in excellent yields, reaction time is less devoid of any side product formation. Operational simplicity, avoidance of anhydrous conditions are the other features which place this protocol at superior position over the already existing procedures.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Reagent grade chemicals were purchased from commercial sources and used as received. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Gemini 300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using silica gel G (Merck).

General procedure for the synthesis of bis-indolylmethanes :

To a stirred solution of carbonyl compound (1 mmol), indole (2 mmol) in methanol (2 ml) at room temperature $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.05 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for time indicated in Table 1. After completion of reaction (Monitored via TLC) the reaction was quenched with water and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×15 mL). The combined organic layer was washed with saturated solution of NaHCO_3 , brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of solvent under reduced pressure gave crude product which was purified by recrystallization from pet. ether : ethyl acetate mixture to afford pure product.

Selected spectral data :

3,3'-bis-Indolylphenylmethane (3a) : m.p. 124–126 °C; IR (KBr) : 3382, 3049, 1640, 1490, 746 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.92 (1H, s), 6.53 (2H, s), 7.03 (2H, t, J 8.1 Hz), 7.09 (2H, t, J 8.1 Hz), 7.34 (9H, m), 7.85 (2H, brs); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 143.8, 137.3, 127.7, 127.2, 126.8, 123.4, 120.8, 119.3, 119.1, 118.7, 112.3, 42.1.

3,3'-bis-Indolyl-2-furylmethane (3d) : m.p. 321–323 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.75 (2H, brs), 7.35–7.66 (9H, m), 7.10 (2H, s), 9.36 (1H, d, J 3.22 Hz), 6.23 (1H, d, J 4.11 Hz), 5.82 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 152.1, 141.2, 136.5, 131.1, 122.7, 121.5, 120.4, 119.5, 112.5, 111.9, 110.3, 102.2, 41.2.

3,3'-bis-Indolyl(4-nitrophenyl)methane (3f) : m.p. 219–221 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.18 (2H, d, J 7.82 Hz), 7.73 (2H, brs), 7.45–7.60 (10H, m), 7.05 (2H, s), 6.02 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 145.3, 143.1, 136.2, 133.9, 130.2, 121.8, 121.2, 120.8, 119.7, 119.7, 112.1, 110.1, 44.6.

3,3'-bis-Indolyldimethylmethane (3i) : m.p. 65–66 °C; IR (KBr) : 3420, 3021, 1655, 1503, 738 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.92 (6H, s), 6.84 (2H, s), 7.03 (2H, m), 7.11 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 7.26 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.94 (2H, brs).

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